

Design of LC Filter with Shunt Damping Resistor for Non-linear Load to Reduce the Total Harmonic Distortion in Load Voltage

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Abstract

The electrical power distribution system is the part of a power system, which supplies electrical power to consumers for utilization. Recently the utilization of non-linear loads has been increasing in the distribution system which badly affected the sinusoidal output voltage waveform. Every consumer of electricity demands consistent and sinusoidal voltage waveform to run their loads properly but due to power quality issues such as harmonics, voltage sag, voltage swell, flickering, and interruption of power supply which badly affect the output voltage of the loads may result in equipment damages, and financial loss. This research study discusses the voltage harmonic which is one of the power quality problems. The harmonic is a non-sinusoidal waveform that is generated due to the applications of non-linear loads which affect the power system reliability, increase the transformer losses, line losses, and frequent faults are generated which results in poor utility revenue, and reduction in production in industries. So, in this research study, the LC filter with a damping resistor is designed to improve the output voltage waveform. The MATLAB simulation model is developed to analyze the performance of the distribution system under linear and non-linear loads with and without an LC filter circuit and also Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) is analyzed through Fast Fourier Transform (FFT).

Index Terms: Fast Fourier Transform, LC Filter, Power Quality issues, Total Harmonic Distortion, and Non-linear load.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently the utilization of non-linear loads has increased in the distribution system and every consumer of electricity demands for consistent power supply to run their loads properly but due to power quality issues such as harmonics, voltage sag, voltage swell, flickering, and interruption of power supply which badly affected the power quality and may result in equipment damages, and financial loss [1]. Non-linear loads in power systems, such as rectifiers, inverters, and variable speed drives, introduce harmonics that distort the load voltage waveform, leading to increased Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) [2]. High THD in power systems can cause a myriad of problems, including overheating of equipment, reduced efficiency, and interference with communication lines [3]. According to a report, line losses are increasing, and frequent faults are generated due to the poor maintenance of the power system or overloading which results in poor utility revenue, and a reduction in the production of industries [4]. The term electric power quality refers to a closed sinusoidal power distribution bus voltage and consumers have voltage at their terminals that must be sinusoidal [5]. The problem of disturbance-free voltage at consumer's premises is not as easy as imagined due to the overloading of transformers, and feeders, theft of electricity, improper maintenance, and power electronic loads [6]. Power

quality has turned into an essential issue for additional reasons such as the financial need for the organizations to build their intensity, the broad utilization of hardware which is delicate to voltage disturbing influences and creates stress itself, and freedom of the power market [7]. In this unique situation, it is fundamental for the utility and the customers to prevent and identify power quality issues and to make reachable arrangements [2], and [8]. The voltage harmonic is one of the power quality problems that are generated due to the applications of non-linear loads [9], so it is very essential to improve the harmonic distorted waveform to improve the quality of output voltage otherwise it will affect the power system reliability, increase in the transformer losses, increase in line losses, and frequently faults are generated which results in poor utility revenue, and reduction in the production of industries [10]. In the previous research, the different types of filters were designed to mitigate the harmonics [11-14]. In this paper, an LC filter with a damping resistor is designed to control the output voltage of the non-linear load. This literature review examines the design and effectiveness of LC filters with shunt damping resistors in reducing THD in load voltage, highlighting key research findings and methodologies [2]. Chen et al. (2020) presented research [15], which focused on optimizing the damping resistor value to achieve the best trade-off between THD reduction and power loss. Their findings

indicate that an optimally designed damping resistor can reduce THD by up to 50% compared to traditional LC filters without damping.

Kumar and Singh (2019) presented research and employed both simulation and experimental setups to validate the performance of LC filters with shunt damping [16]. Their results confirmed significant improvements in voltage waveform quality and a substantial reduction in harmonic content.

Recent advancements include adaptive LC filters or adaptive filtering techniques that adjust the damping resistor dynamically based on load conditions. These adaptive systems, as described by Zhao and Wang (2021), offer superior performance by continuously tuning the filter parameters to minimize THD in real-time [17].

The performance of a proposed system is analyzed through MATLAB Simulink Software with and without an LC filter. The proposed power system with an LC filter is shown in figure I.

Figure I: Proposed Power System

The rest of this article is divided into the following sections:

The electrical power distribution system is described in Section II. In Section III, Electrical loads are defined. Section IV presents the LC filter design, while Section V presents the proposed power system. Section VI summarizes the conclusions.

II. ELECTRICAL POWER DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM

The electrical Power system is divided into Generation, Transmission, and Distribution systems to supply the power to the consumers for utilization. Due to the increasing number of electronic devices; consumers are facing non sinusoidal voltage, which is not acceptable to run their appliances properly [18]. The power quality problems are increasing throughout the world. The transient is an unexpectedly large increase in voltage or current levels caused by external forces such as lightning, load exchanging, or wire broken which may result in damage to devices [19]. The voltage sag is a reduction in voltage from 10 to 90% of the supply voltage for a short period of time i.e., half cycle to 1 minute is known as voltage sag, caused by switching ON of heavy loads, faults, etc. This may cause failure of sensitive equipment [20]. The voltage swell is an increase in the voltage from 110% to 180% caused by switching off the heavy loads etc. The harmonic is defined as the sinusoidal waveform and can be represented with several periodic functions caused by power electronic devices.

The power quality problems are shown in figure II [21].

Figure II: Power Quality Problems in the Distribution System

III. ELECTRICAL LOADS

Electrical loads are the part of electrical circuits in which current is sent for production [22]. A load can convert electricity into heat, motion, and light, such as a bulb, motor, etc. Linear and non-linear are the types of electrical loads, which are commonly used in distribution systems [23].

A. Linear Loads

The load that has no distortion in its load voltage is known as a linear load, such as a resistive load in which current and voltage remain in phase. The inductive loads are loads in which the current lags behind the voltage by 90°, and capacitive loads in which the voltage leads to the current by 90° [24]. Examples of linear loads are heaters, induction motors, transformers, and capacitors.

B. Non-linear Loads

The load in which the current is not proportional to the voltage and gives distorted output voltage and current waveform is known as a non-linear load [25]. These types of loads are commonly used nowadays such as computers, printers, televisions, transistors, and rectifiers which result in distorted output voltage. So it is necessary to improve the output voltage waveform of non-linear loads otherwise it will affect the connected sensitive loads [11]. In this research paper, the LC filter is designed to compensate for the harmonics generated by nonlinear loads.

When the non-linear load is switched ON, then:

$$\frac{d}{dt} i_l = -\frac{1}{L_{dc}} U_o + \frac{1}{L_{dc}} U_{Line} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} U_o = \frac{1}{C_{dc}} I_i - \frac{1}{C_{dc}} I_o \quad (2)$$

When the non-linear load is switched OFF then:

$$\frac{d}{dt} U_o = -\frac{1}{C_{dc}} I_o \quad (3)$$

$$I_L = 0 \quad (4)$$

Where:

U_o represents the DC voltage,
 i_l is the load current of non-linear load,
 L_{DC} and C_{DC} are the inductor current, and,
 capacitor DC side LC filter.

The dynamic response of non-linear load is given in equations i.e., eq. (1-4) respectively. Figure III shows the circuit diagram of non-linear load.

Figure III: Non-Linear Load

IV. DESIGN OF LC FILTER FOR PROPOSED POWER SYSTEM

The filter plays a vital role in smoothing the current and voltage waveforms [26]. The utilization of non-linear loads such as laptops, printers, desktops, servers, inverters, matrix converters, etc., is increasing day by day, which results in non-sinusoidal voltage and current waveforms at the output of load [14]. It is necessary to mitigate the harmonics to achieve sinusoidal voltage and current because most of the loads are very sensitive to variations in voltage and may cause damage or failure [13]. In this research paper, the LC filter is designed to mitigate the problem of harmonics at the output of the load [12]. There are some possible ways to design an LC filter by connecting the resistor in series or parallel with a capacitor to get a better output waveform [27]. Figure IV shows the simple LC filter with a resistor and capacitor.

Figure IV: (a) LC Filter; (b) LC Filter with Resistor and Capacitor

We can get the output impedance and voltage gain of the filter through the below equations i.e., eq. (6), and eq. (7).

$$Z_0 = \frac{sL(1+sRC_2)}{s^3LRC_1C_2+s^2L(C_1+C_2)+sRC_2+1} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{V_c}{V_s} = \frac{(1+sRC_2)}{s^3LRC_1C_2+s^2L(C_1+C_2)+sRC_2+1} \quad (6)$$

By re-arranging equation (6) we obtained equation (7):

$$H(s) = -R = -\frac{1}{k} = \frac{s^2L(C_1+C_2+1)}{s^3LRC_1C_2+sC_2} \quad (7)$$

Where:

$H(s)$ is the root locus plot of a closed loop system with an open loop transfer function, and,

K is the variable feedback gain.

In order to design the LC filter the input voltage must be known and calculation of the load current, after the calculation of load current the inductor current must be calculated which is almost 20% of the load current then you can calculate the L and C values by equations i.e., eq. (8) and eq. (9).

$$\Delta I_{lmax} = \frac{V}{4 \times L \times F_{SW}} \quad (8)$$

$$F_C = \frac{1}{2 \times \pi \times \sqrt{LC}} \quad (9)$$

Where:

F_{SW} is output power,

I_l is the inductor current,

L is the inductance, and,

C is the capacitance.

In this research paper, an LC filter is designed with a damping resistor which is shown in figure V to get the distortion-free voltage at the load side.

Figure V: LC Filter with Shunt Damping Resistor

V. PROPOSED POWER SYSTEM

In this research study the 11Kv source voltage is taken from the grid station, and a step-down distribution transformer is utilized to reduce the voltage i.e., 11Kv/400v. The three-phase load of 10Kw and the non-linear load are connected to analyze the output voltage before the LC filter and after the LC filter.

Figure VI shows the simulation model of the proposed power system.

A. Simulation Results and Discussion

In MATLAB simulation results following parameters are utilized to get the values of output voltage before and after the application of the LC filter are tabulated in table I.

Table I: Parameters of Proposed Power System

Parameters	Value
Supply Voltage	11Kv
Three-phase Transformer (Step Down)	11KV/400 volts
Filter Inductance	0.1milli Henry
Filter Capacitance	550 micro farad
Filter Resistance	1Ω
Three-phase Load	10 KW
Load Voltage	327 volts

B. Simulation Results with Linear Loads

Figure VI shows the simulation results of the proposed system with linear load without an LC filter.

It is seen that the output voltage of the load is sinusoidal and harmonics are not produced. The value of THD is also analysed through FFT is shown in figure VII.

Figure VI: Simulation Model of Proposed Power System

(a)

(b)

Figure VII: (a) Output Voltage; (b) THD% of Linear Load

C. Simulation Results with Non-Linear Load without LC Filter

Figure VIII shows the simulation results and THD of the proposed system with non-linear loads without an LC

filter. It is seen that the output voltage of the load is not sinusoidal and harmonics are produced due to the connection of non-linear load.

(a)

(b)

Figure VIII: (a) Output Voltage; (b) THD% of Non-Linear Load without LC Filter

D. Simulation Results with Non-Linear Load with LC Filter

Figure IX shows the simulation results and THD of the proposed system with an LC filter. It is seen that the output voltage of the load is sinusoidal and harmonics are reduced due to the connection of the LC filter.

The performance is not satisfactory with nonlinear loads without an LC filter. So THD at the output of load voltage is not within the limit prescribed by the IEEE. So it is necessary to connect the LC filter with nonlinear loads in order to get the sinusoidal voltage waveform at the output of the load voltage.

E. Discussion

The performance of the proposed power system is analyzed through MATLAB Simulink Software.

(a)

(b)

Figure IX: (a) Output Voltage; (b) THD% of Non-Linear Load with LC Filter

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The distribution system is the part of the power system that supplies the electrical power to consumers for utilization. The performance of the proposed power system is analyzed with applications of linear and non-linear loads with and without an LC filter. It is seen that the load side voltage is sinusoidal with linear loads without an LC filter and THD is analyzed through FFT is 0.53% which is within the permissible limit of IEEE standards. The performance of the proposed system is analyzed with non-linear load, so it has been seen that the output voltage is distorted and the THD is 23.09% which is not acceptable as per IEEE standards, so it is necessary to add an LC filter to smooth the output voltage waveform. The THD of non-linear loads with an LC filter is 0.72% which is within the IEEE standards. So it is concluded that the applications of non-linear loads are increasing so it is necessary to add the LC filter to smooth the output voltage waveform.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media. The information obtained from all of the sources is properly recognized and cited below.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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